

ILK O'RTA ASRLARGA OID MUG' ARXIVINING TOPILISHI VA O'RGANILISHI**Muyiddinov Bekali**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ilk o'rta asrlarda o'lkamiz hududidan topilgan dastlabki arxiv hujjatlaridan biri Mug' arxivining topilishi undagi hujjatlar haqida kengroq fikrlar bildirib o'tilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: Sug'd, Markaziy Osiyo, Mug', A.A. Freyman, I.Yu. Krachkovkiy, O.I. Smirnova, M.M. Ishoqov, Tuproqqal'a, Samarqand, Xorazm, xo'jalik, hujjat, arablar, qog'oz.

ОТКРЫТИЕ И ИЗУЧЕНИЕ АРХИВА МУГОВ РАННЕГО СРЕДНЕВЕКОВЬЯ

Аннотация. В этой статье излагаются более широкие соображения по поводу документов, содержащихся в Находке архива Мугов, одного из самых ранних архивных документов, найденных на территории нашей страны в раннем средневековье.

Ключевые слова: Согд, Среднеазиатский, Мугский, А.А. Фрейман, И.Ю. Крачковский, О.И. Смирнова, М.М. Исхаков, земляная крепость, Самарканд, Хорезм, ферма, документ, арабы, бумага.

DISCOVERY AND STUDY OF THE MUG ARCHIVE DATING BACK TO THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES

Abstract. In this article, the discovery of one of the earliest archival documents found in the territory of our country in the early Middle Ages, The Mug archive, has given broader views on the documents contained in it.

Key words: Sugd, Central Asia, Mug, A.A. Freiman, I.Yu. Krachkovky, O.I. Smirnova, M.M. Ishakov, soil, Samarkand, Khwarezm, farm, document, Arabs, paper.

O'lkamiz madaniyati tarixida muhim rol o'ynagan sug'd yozuvi mil. av. III-II asrlarda shakllangan. Buyuk Ipak yo'li va uning shaxobchalari bo'ylab sug'd tili va yozuvi ham keng tarqala borgan. Ettisuv, Xo'tan, Mo'g'iliston hududlarida sug'd yozuvlarining topilishi buning isbotidir. Sug'diylar uch turdagi: bevosita sug'd, manixey va suriya yozuvlaridan foydalanganlar.

Sug'd yozuvi orqali bizgacha eramizning boshlaridan to X-XI asrlarga qadar yozilgan ko'plab noyob yodgorliklar yetib kelgan. Ular orasida ko'plab numizmatik materiallar (tanga yozuvlari), metall, sopol, yog'och, charm, qog'oz va boshqa buyumlarga bitilgan tekstlar, shaxsiy maktublar, diniy, axloqiy-falsafiy tekstlarning parchalari, xo'jalik, huquqiy va diplomatik hujjatlar bor. Ana shunday yodgorliklarning katta guruhi 1932-1933 yillarda Tojikistonning Panjikent shahri yaqinidagi Mug' tog'i tepasidagi qadimgi qasr xarobasidan topilgan sug'd hujjatlaridir.

Oradan 87 yil vaqt o'tishiga qaramay bu hujjatlar hali hanuz o'zining lingvistik, matnnavislik va tarixiy ahamiyatini yo'qotgan emas. Qolaversa, keyinchalik "Mug' arxivi hujjatlari" deb atalgan bu manbaning topilishi VII asr oxiri – VIII asr birinchi choragi Markaziy Osiyo mintaqasida ro'y bergan siyosiy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va etnomadaniy jarayonlar masalasiga bir qadar oydinlik kiritdi.

Yillar davomida o'rganilib kelinayotgan mazkur arxiv hujjatlari sobiq sovet va hozirgi o'zbek sug'dshunosligi taraqqiyoti uchun muhim rol o'ynadi. Xususan, XX asr ikkinchi choragidan boshlab sobiq Ittifoqda sug'dshunoslikning fan sohasi sifatida rivojlanishida Mug' arxivi hujjatlarini katta o'rni bor. E'tirof etish kerakki, sovet davri tadqiqotchilari hujjatlarni o'rganish ishiga salmoqli ulush qo'shdilar.

Dastlab hujjatlar ekspeditsiya rahbari A.A. Freyman tomonidan moddiy ashyo sifatida izchil o'rganildi. Aniqlanishicha, bu hujjatlar teri, qog'oz va yog'och parchalariga yozilgan bo'lib, shaxsiy va diplomatik xatlar, bitimlar, taqvimlar, xo'jalik va hisob qaytlaridan iborat bo'lgan. Ulardan ikkitasi arabcha, uchtasi xitoycha va bittasi runiy yozuvida bitilgan. Qolganlari esa sug'diy til va yozuvida bo'lib, barcha hujjatlar Sug'd konfederatsiyasining Panch viloyati va uning markazi Panjikent shahri hokimi Devashtich saroyida saqlangan, ya'ni saroy devonxonasining arxivi hisoblangan. A.A. Freyman o'z ekspeditsiyasi aniqlagan 74 ta hujjatning barchasini tavsifladi, yirik va ahamiyatlilarini esa tarjima qilib, ularning ayrimlariga sharhlar berdi. Avvaliga, ya'ni 1934 yildan "Согдийский сборник" da nashr etila boshlangan ma'lumotlar, so'ngra 1962-yilda yaxlit to'plam holda nashrdan chiqdi. Ayni vaqtda arabshunos mutaxassis I.Yu. Krachkovkiy Mug' arxividagi ayrim arab tilli hujjatlarning tarjimasini va talqinini e'lon qildi.

Mug' arxivi hujjatlarining katta kompleksi – yuridik hujjatlar va maktublar yirik sug'dshunos olim V.A. Livshits tomonidan ilmiy jihatdan chuqur o'rganilib, lingvistik va tarixiy izohlari bilan nashr etildi. Mazkur nashrda ilk o'rta asrlarda nafaqat Sug'dda, balki Markaziy Osiyo mintaqasida kechgan siyosiy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, ma'naviy, madaniy va mafkuraviy jarayonlar chuqur tahlil etildi. Xususan, hujjatlarda aks etgan voqealar markazi bo'lgan Panch viloyati va Panjikent shahrining arab istilosi chog'idagi holati misolida butun mintaqadagi jarayonlar tizimini ko'rsatib berishga harakat qilindi. Ayrim yevrotsentrizm qarashlaridan farqli ravishda istiloga qarshi kurashdagi turk-sug'd ittifoqi masalasiga xolis yondashildi.

Mug' arxivi hujjatlarini o'rganish borasida O.I. Smirnovaning munosib o'rni bor. U 1962-yilda eronshunos olim M.N. Bogolyubov bilan hamkorlikda Mug' arxividan aynan xo'jalik mazmunidagi hujjatlarni ajratib olib, ularni tahlil etdi va nashrdan chiqardi. Bundan tashqari O. I. Smirnova Mug' arxivida keltirilgan ilk o'rta asrlardagi Sug'dning siyosiy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy tarixini tadqiq etish bilan birga Sug'd numizmatikasini ham izchil o'rgandi. Manba va numizmatik materiallarni qiyosiy o'rganib, ular o'zaro to'ldirildi.

Bu kabi tadqiqotlar natijasida ilk o'rta asrlarda mintaqamizda ro'y bergan tarixiy jarayonlar ancha oydinlashdi. O'zbekistonda Mug' arxivini o'rganish jarayoni V.A. Livshitsning izdoshi M.M. Ishoqov nomi bilan bog'liq.

Tadqiqotchi sug'diy tili va mintaqada yozuv madaniyati tarixi bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib bordi. Bu borada Mug' arxivi hujjatlaridan ham samarali foydalanildi. Sug'dshunoslik, avestoshunoslik va xorazmshunoslik sohalarining aynan O'zbekistonda rivoj topishi uchun qator ishlarni amalga oshirdi. Endilikda ilmiy ish olib boradigan tadqiqotchilar oldida turgan vazifa – yozma manbalarning avvalgi matnshunoslik va lingvistik tahlillaridan kelib chiqib, har bitta hujjatning yozilish tarixi, hujjat bilan bog'liq tarixiy jarayonlarni izchil o'rganish bo'lib qolmoqda.

Mug' arxividagi birinchi raqamli hujjatda O'rta Osiyoning arablar tomonidan istilo etilishi davri, ya'ni 720-722 yillardagi siyosiy voqealar aks etgan. Voqealarning ishtirokchilari aynan hujjatlar orqali ko'z o'ngimizda namoyon bo'ladi. Ularning qanday mavqega ega bo'lganligi hamda siyosiy jarayonlarga qay darajada ta'sir etganligi tarixiy nuqtai nazardan muhimdir. Aynan hujjatining tavsifiga keladigan bo'lsak, mazkur hujjat ko'p sonli Mug' arxivi hujjatlari qatorida 1932-yilning bahorida Tojikiston Respublikasi Zahmatobod tumani Haydarobod qishlog'ida yashovchi cho'pon Jo'raali Mahmudali tomonidan topilgan. Savat ichida joylashtirilgan ipak qog'ozga notanish harflar bilan yozilgan hujjatlar bir necha oylar davomida qo'ldan-qo'lga o'tib yurdi.

Nihoyat, o'sha vaqtlarda Zahmatobod tumani kompartiya qo'mitasi kotibi bo'lib ishlagan Abdulhamid Puloti sa'yi harakati bilan hujjatlar Dushanbe shahriga olib kelindi. Bu erda ularni qadimgi so'g'd tilida yozilganligi aniqlangandan so'ng, fotonusxalari Leningrad (Sankt-Peterburg) professori A.A. Freymanga o'rganib chiqishga yuborilgan edi. Ipak tolalari aralashmasidan tayyorlangan yuqa oqish-kulrang qog'ozga bitilgan bu hujjat yaxshi saqlanib qolgan. Uning hajmi 28,9x28,2 o'lchamda bo'lib, deyarli to'rtburchak shaklda bo'lgan. Uning barcha 23 qatori to'liq saqlangan. Qog'oz to'rtga buklangani bois, buklangan izlaridan yirtila boshlagan. Qog'ozning chap burchagidan ozgina uzilgan. Ammo matn qismi zarar ko'rmagan. Varaqning ostki qismida unga shirach bilan ikkinchi bir qog'oz ulangan. Ammo bu parcha saqlanmagan, faqatgina qog'oz izlari qolgan xolos. Uni ilk bor tadqiq qilgan A.A. Freyman dastlab hujjatning maktub ko'rinishida ekanligiga e'tibor qaratgan. O'qish jarayonida bu maktub Panch hukumdori Devashtichga yo'llanganligi aniqlangan. Sababi hujjat "Sug'd podshosi, Samarqand hokimi Devashtichga yuborilgan deb boshlanar edi. Yuqoriga tahlil etilgan O'rta Osiyo hududidan topilgan Nisadagi Parfiya arxivi, shimoliy Afg'onistondan topilgan Baqtriya arxivi, qadimgi Xorazmdagi Tuproqqal'a arxivi va Mug' tog'idan topilgan arxiv hujjatlari bizga mintaqamizda ro'y bergan siyosiy voqealar xususida ma'lumot beradi.

Qolaversa, bu hujjatlar tarixiy shaxslar faoliyatiga to'g'ri baho berish, ularning yutuq va kamchiliklaridan xulosa chiqarish, eng asosiysi tarixiy saboq uchun yordam beradi.

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